

Improving Medication Adherence Among Patients with Hypertension Through a Hybrid Health Educational Intervention Based on the Health Belief Model in Rural Indonesia: A Quasi-Experimental Difference-in-Differences Study

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Abstract

Background: Hypertension remains a major global health challenge, particularly in low- and middle-income countries, where medication adherence is essential for blood pressure control. Hybrid educational approaches combining face-to-face and digital strategies offer practical solutions in resource-limited settings.

Objective: To evaluate the effectiveness of a Hybrid Health Education Intervention based on the Health Belief Model (HHEI-HBM) among patients with hypertension in rural Indonesia.

Methodology: A pre-post control-group quasi-experimental study was conducted in two randomly selected community health centres (CHCs) in Majalengka, Indonesia (one intervention and one control). Participants were recruited consecutively. Of 129 eligible individuals, 110 met the criteria and were analysed (51 in the intervention group; 59 in the control group). Behavioural outcomes were measured using validated questionnaires, and blood pressure was measured with a validated digital device. Baseline equivalence was tested using chi-square tests and independent t-tests. Intervention effects were estimated using a Difference-in-Differences (DiD) approach.

Results: A DiD analysis demonstrated that HHEI-HBM significantly improved knowledge ($\beta = 1.72$; 95% CI: 0.68–2.76; $p = 0.001$), self-efficacy ($\beta = 6.16$; 95% CI: 3.42–8.91; $p < 0.001$), and medication adherence ($\beta = 1.28$; 95% CI: 0.49–2.07; $p = 0.002$). Significant reductions were observed in systolic blood pressure ($\beta = -9.67$ mmHg; 95% CI: -12.42 to -6.91; $p < 0.001$) and diastolic blood pressure ($\beta = -2.80$ mmHg; 95% CI: -3.91 to -1.69; $p < 0.001$).

Conclusion: HHEI-HBM improved behavioural outcomes and reduced blood pressure among rural patients with hypertension.

Unique Contribution: This study demonstrates the effectiveness of a multimodal educational approach integrating complementary strategies in resource-limited CHCs, while reinforcing the HBM as a robust framework for behaviour change interventions.

Key Recommendation: Integration of HHEI-HBM into routine health promotion programmes in rural CHCs is recommended. Larger studies with longer follow-up are needed to confirm sustainability and support implementation.

Keywords: Medication adherence; Hypertension; Hybrid Health Education Intervention; Health Belief Model; Difference-in-Differences; Indonesia

Introduction

Hypertension remains a major global health problem and a leading cause of cardiovascular morbidity and mortality. As a key risk factor for heart disease, stroke, and kidney failure, its prevalence continues to rise, particularly in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) (Hu et al., 2023). The number of adults with hypertension increased from 1.39 billion in 2010 to a projected 1.56 billion by 2025, with a higher burden in LMICs (31.5%; ~1.04 billion) than in high-income countries (28.5%; ~349 million), highlighting global disparities (Mills et al., 2020). From 1990 to 2020, prevalence in LMICs rose steadily, especially in rural areas, underscoring the need for context-specific interventions targeting rural populations to reduce the disease burden (Ranzani et al., 2022).

Although antihypertensive therapy is widely available and effective, its success depends heavily on consistent medication adherence (Hamrahian, 2020). Globally, non-adherence is associated with poorer clinical outcomes, higher hospitalisation rates, and greater risk of preventable cardiovascular events. These challenges are more severe in rural settings, where healthcare access is limited and socioeconomic barriers further obstruct blood pressure control.

In Indonesia, hypertension prevalence is 30.8%, with substantial gaps in diagnosis and treatment between adults aged 18–59 and those ≥ 60 years. Only 5.9% of younger adults are diagnosed, 2.53% adhere to medication, and 2.34% attend follow-ups, compared with 22.9%, 11.9%, and 11% in older adults. Rural–urban disparities persist, with lower adherence and treatment education in rural areas, contributing to poor blood pressure control and disability. Among individuals ≥ 15 years, 59.1% of disability is from acquired diseases, 53.5% of which are non-communicable, mainly hypertension (Ministry of Health of the Republic of Indonesia, 2024). In Majalengka, the 2018 Basic Health Research reported that only 9.66% of patients regularly monitored their blood pressure; 48.65% occasionally; and 41.69% did not routinely, thereby increasing the risk of uncontrolled hypertension. In 2021, the Majalengka District Health Office recorded hypertension service coverage at 75.78% of the target, highlighting persistent gaps.

Hypertension non-adherence stems from socioeconomic and psychological barriers. The Health Belief Model (HBM) explains that perceived susceptibility, severity, benefits, and barriers shape health behaviour. In hypertension, low perceived threat and high perceived barriers are important predictors of non-adherence (Alyafei & Easton-Carr, 2025). Digital approaches tend to be more effective among younger populations, whereas face-to-face methods may better suit older adults (Wahab, 2025). Therefore, combining digital and face-to-face methods interventions to strengthen perceived benefits and reduce barriers is essential.

To address this, the present study developed an HBM-based health education programme using a hybrid approach. In this study, the hybrid approach refers to integrating structured face-to-face educational sessions with continuous digital support via WhatsApp, including medication reminders, reinforcement of health knowledge, and interactive communication between patients and healthcare providers. This model aims to retain personal interaction while improving accessibility in rural Indonesian settings. This study aimed to evaluate the effectiveness of the HHEI-HBM, compared with standard health education, in improving knowledge, self-efficacy, medication adherence, and blood pressure among patients with hypertension in rural Indonesia.

Materials and Methods

Study design and setting

This study employed a quasi-experimental design with a pre-test and post-test control group. The research was conducted in Majalengka Regency, West Java, Indonesia. Majalengka Regency is one of Indonesia's regencies where the majority of the population lives in rural areas. Two Community Health Centres (CHCs) were randomly selected as research sites to represent the intervention and control settings.

Participants and sampling

The sample size was calculated using G*Power 3.1.9.7 software to ensure adequate statistical power. The mean difference and standard deviation values used for the sample calculation were obtained from a previous meta-analysis study, with a mean difference in adherence of 0.69 (95% CI: 0.25–1.12) (Tan et al., 2019), a statistical power level of 0.90, and a significance level of 0.05 (two-tailed). The calculation resulted in a minimum required sample size of 46 participants per group. To anticipate potential dropouts during the research process, the sample size was increased by 19 participants per group, resulting in a total of 65 participants in each group.

A multistage sampling technique was applied. In the first stage, two CHCs were selected randomly using cluster random sampling; both were rural and operated within the same primary healthcare system, ensuring comparable service delivery and resource availability. In the second stage, participants were selected using a consecutive sampling method according to predetermined criteria. The inclusion criteria were: (1) age between 15 and 60 years; (2) diagnosed with hypertension; (3) currently taking antihypertensive medication; and (4) having attended at least one clinical visit. The exclusion criteria were: (1) pregnant women; (2) severe cognitive impairment; (3) serious complications; and (4) known secondary causes of hypertension. After selection and follow-up, a total of 110 eligible adult patients with hypertension were included in

the final analysis, comprising 51 participants in the intervention group and 59 in the control group. The complete participant selection process is illustrated in **Figure 1**.

Figure 1. Participant selection process

Instruments

The validity and reliability of all instruments were verified before the main analysis to ensure the robustness of the findings. Behavioural aspect data, including knowledge, were measured using the Indonesian version of the Hypertension Knowledge Level Scale (HK-LS) (Ernawati et al., 2020). This instrument was re-tested for validity and reliability, with total inter-item correlation validity (r) values ranging from 0.387 to 0.713 (r -table = 0.361; $n = 30$; $\alpha = 0.05$) and a Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficient of 0.886. Self-efficacy was measured using the Indonesian version of the MASES-R questionnaire (Ivana, 2020), which was re-tested for validity and reliability, showing r values ranging from 0.391 to 0.680 (r -table = 0.361; $n = 30$; $\alpha = 0.05$) and a Cronbach's alpha of 0.788. Medication adherence was assessed using the Indonesian version of the MMAS-8

questionnaire (Riani et al., 2017), which demonstrated validity coefficients ranging from 0.419 to 0.662 ($r\text{-table} = 0.361$; $n = 30$; $\alpha = 0.05$) and a Cronbach's alpha of 0.642. Clinical data, specifically blood pressure measurements, were obtained using a validated digital sphygmomanometer (Sinocare model BSX516), with a measurement range of 0–290 mmHg, ± 3 mmHg accuracy, and a cuff size suitable for adult upper-arm circumference (22–24 cm).

The Indonesian HK-LS comprises 22 items (1 point for correct, 0 for incorrect; total 0–22). The MASES-R includes 13 statements rated on a 4-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 ('not confident') to 4 ('very confident'), for a total of 13–52. Similarly, the eight-item MMAS-8 is scored 1 for adherence and 0 for non-adherence, with a total score of 0–8. Trained enumerators administered the questionnaires through face-to-face interviews to ensure participant comprehension.

Procedure for data collection

Data collection was conducted at two measurement points: before the intervention (pre-test) and after completion of the entire intervention programme (post-test). Data were obtained through structured interviews using questionnaires, with an average duration of approximately 10 minutes per respondent. At the pre-test stage, data were collected to assess knowledge of hypertension, self-efficacy, and medication adherence using structured questionnaires administered by trained enumerators. Systolic and diastolic blood pressure measurements were performed by competent healthcare personnel using standardised protocols. Following completion of all intervention sessions, post-test measurements were conducted using procedures identical to those used at the pre-test to ensure consistency in data collection methods. Variables measured at post-test included knowledge of hypertension, self-efficacy, medication adherence, and systolic and diastolic blood pressure.

Intervention of HBM-based hybrid health education

The intervention group received an HBM-based Hybrid Health Education programme comprising six sessions: two face-to-face health education sessions lasting 15–20 minutes each and four delivered via WhatsApp group on the first day of each week. The face-to-face sessions aimed to improve patients' understanding of hypertension, enhance patients' confidence in taking medication regularly, and foster commitment between patients and healthcare providers acting as facilitators. Health education delivered through the WhatsApp group aimed to provide repetition and reinforcement of the material, and to facilitate continuous communication among patients and between patients and healthcare providers regarding the educational content. Meanwhile, the control group received standard health education through monthly community health education at the CHC. The treatment summary is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Summary of Content, Objectives, Methods, and Weekly Sessions of the HBM-based Hybrid Health Education

Time	Content	Purpose	Method
Week 1	Patients received health education on "Overview of Hypertension and Risk of Complications (Introduction to Hypertension)."	To understand hypertension blood pressure thresholds, symptoms of hypertension, risk	Healthcare staff delivered the material through face-to-face meetings, followed by a quiz on the topic.

Time	Content	Purpose	Method
		factors, and the risks of uncontrolled hypertension complications.	
Week 2	Patients received health education on “Hypertension Control through Healthy Lifestyle Practices,” including: Routine health checks, eliminating exposure to cigarette smoke, engaging in regular physical activity, balanced diet, adequate rest, and stress management (abbreviated as CERDIK in Indonesian).	To understand the benefits of a healthy lifestyle and blood pressure control in managing hypertension.	Healthcare staff delivered the material via digital flyers and animated videos in a WhatsApp group. Staff also reminded patients to take their medication regularly and assessed their understanding of the provided material.
Week 3	Patients received health education on “Hypertension Control through Regular Medication.”	To understand the benefits of regularly taking antihypertensive medication.	Material was delivered via WhatsApp group using digital flyers and animated videos. Staff reminded patients to take medication regularly and assessed their understanding of the topic.
Week 4	Patients received health education on “Identifying Treatment Barriers in Hypertension Control.”	To understand and identify barriers to taking antihypertensive medication.	Material was delivered via WhatsApp group using digital flyers and animated videos. Staff reminded patients to take medication regularly and assessed their understanding of the topic.
Week 5	Patients received health education on “Strategies to Improve Adherence to Regular Treatment.”	To increase self-confidence in taking medication regularly.	Material was delivered via WhatsApp group using digital flyers and animated videos. Staff reminded patients to take medication regularly and assessed their understanding of the topic.
Week 6	Patients received health education on “Providing Motivation to Strengthen Patients’ Attitudes and Self-Belief in Controlling Hypertension.”	To maintain self-confidence in taking medication regularly.	Healthcare staff delivered materials during face-to-face meetings and assessed patients’ confidence in their intention to adhere to medication.

Data analysis

Statistical analyses were conducted in Stata 17. Descriptive statistics summarised participant characteristics and variable distributions. Between-group differences were assessed using chi-square tests for categorical variables and independent t-tests or Mann–Whitney U tests for continuous variables, depending on data distribution. Two-tailed tests were applied throughout. Intervention effectiveness was evaluated using a Difference-in-Differences (DiD) regression

model estimating the interaction between time and treatment group, with results reported as coefficients and 95% confidence intervals. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

Results

Table 2 shows the results of the equivalency analysis between groups and the DiD analysis used in this study.

Table 2: Baseline Comparison of Characteristics Between Two Groups Before the Implementation of the HBM-Based Hybrid Health Education

Characteristics	Intervention Group	Control Group	p-value
	(n=51) n (%)	(n=59) n (%)	
Sex			
Male	11 (21.57)	10 (16.95)	0.539 ^a
Female	40 (78.43)	49 (83.05)	
Education Level			
Elementary School	13 (25.49)	27 (45.76)	0.076 ^a
Junior High School	17 (33.33)	10 (16.95)	
Senior High School	19 (37.25)	18 (30.51)	
Higher Education	2 (3.92)	4 (6.78)	
Occupation			
Farmer	2 (3.92)	0 (0)	0.114 ^b
Trader	8 (15.69)	7 (11.86)	
Entrepreneur	7 (13.73)	7 (11.86)	
Village Official	3 (5.88)	6 (10.17)	
Homemaker	30 (58.82)	33 (55.93)	
Civil Servant	1 (1.96)	0 (0)	
Labourer	0 (0)	6 (10.17)	
First Informant at Hypertension Diagnosis			
Midwife	12 (23.53)	20 (33.90)	0.438 ^a
Doctor	26 (50.98)	24 (40.68)	
Nurse	13 (25.49)	15 (25.42)	
Year of Hypertension Diagnosis			
Awareness			
2025	10 (19.61)	8 (13.56)	0.333 ^a
2024	18 (35.29)	15 (25.42)	
2019-2023	17 (33.33)	23 (38.98)	
<2019	6 (11.76)	13 (22.03)	
Place of Hypertension Treatment			
Integrated Health Post (<i>Posbindu</i>)	10 (19.61)	17 (28.81)	0.096 ^a
Community Health Centre (<i>Puskesmas</i>)	26 (50.98)	19 (32.20)	
Private Clinic	11 (21.57)	11 (18.64)	
Private Midwife/Health Worker Practice	4 (7.84)	12 (20.34)	
Number of Antihypertensive Drug Types			
1 Type	49 (96.08)	57 (96.61)	0.882 ^a
2 Types	2 (3.92)	2 (3.39)	
Presence of Other Illness/Complaints			
Yes	24 (47.06)	37 (62.71)	0.100 ^a
No	27 (52.94)	22 (37.29)	
Distance to Healthcare Facility			
Near	41 (80.39)	42 (71.19)	0.263 ^a
Far	10 (19.61)	17 (28.81)	
Travel Time to Healthcare Facility			

Characteristics	Intervention Group	Control Group	p-value
	(n=51)	(n=59)	
	n (%)	n (%)	
Short	37 (72.55)	41 (69.49)	0.725 ^a
Long	14 (27.45)	18 (30.51)	
Age			
Mean ± SD	47.24 ± 6.85	47.56 ± 8.36	0.826 ^c
Knowledge			
Mean ± SD	17.00 ± 3.14	17.73 ± 2.88	0.290 ^d
Self-efficacy			
Mean ± SD	37.39 ± 7.45	38.58 ± 7.48	0.409 ^c
Medication Adherence			
Mean ± SD	3.92 ± 2.04	4.15 ± 1.71	0.339 ^d
Systolic Blood Pressure			
Mean ± SD	169.73 ± 13.77	165.01 ± 15.02	0.091 ^c
Diastolic Blood Pressure			
Mean ± SD	93.95 ± 5.53	93.13 ± 4.72	0.270 ^c

Notes: ^a Chi-square test; ^b Fisher’s exact test; ^c Independent t-test; ^d Mann–Whitney test; Significant if p-value < 0.05

Table 2 shows that 110 participants were included, with 51 in the intervention group and 59 in the control group. In the intervention group, most were female (78.43%), senior high school graduates (37.25%), homemakers (58.82%), diagnosed in 2024 (35.29%), treated at a CHC (50.98%), prescribed one medication (96.08%), without other illnesses (52.94%), living near the facility (80.39%) with short travel time (72.55%), and had a mean age of 47.24 years. Mean scores were knowledge 17.00, self-efficacy 37.39, medication adherence 3.92, systolic BP 169.73 mmHg, and diastolic BP 93.95 mmHg. In the control group, most were female (83.05%), primary school graduates (46.76%), homemakers (55.93%), diagnosed between 2019–2023 (38.98%), treated at a CHC (32.20%), prescribed one medication (96.61%), with other illnesses (62.71%), living near the facility (71.19%) with short travel time (69.49%), and had a mean age of 47.56 years. Mean scores were knowledge 17.73, self-efficacy 38.58, medication adherence 4.15, systolic BP 165.01 mmHg, and diastolic BP 93.13 mmHg. Independence tests for all variables yielded $p > 0.05$, indicating comparable baseline characteristics, knowledge, self-efficacy, medication adherence, and blood pressure between groups.

Table 3: DiD Comparison Between the Intervention Group and Control Group After the Implementation of HBM-Based Hybrid Health Education

Variable / Group	Pre-test Mean ± SD	Post-test Mean ± SD	Adjusted DiD* Coefficient ± SE	95% CI	p-value
Knowledge					
Experimental	17.00 ± 3.14	19.06 ± 1.68	1.72 ± 0.52	0.68 – 2.76	0.001
Control	17.73 ± 2.88	18.07 ± 2.34			
Self-efficacy					
Experimental	37.39 ± 7.45	44.10 ± 4.39	6.16 ± 1.39	3.42 – 8.91	<0.001
Control	38.58 ± 7.48	39.12 ± 8.50			
MA					
Experimental	3.92 ± 2.04	5.75 ± 1.21	1.28 ± 0.40	0.49 – 2.07	0.002

Variable / Group	Pre-test Mean ± SD	Post-test Mean ± SD	Adjusted DiD* Coefficient ± SE	95% CI	p-value
Control	4.15 ± 1.71	4.69 ± 2.00			
SBP					
Experimental	169.73 ± 13.77	161.63 ± 14.04	-9.67 ± 1.39	-12.42 to -6.91	<0.001
Control	165.01 ± 15.02	166.58 ± 14.18			
DBP					
Experimental	93.95 ± 5.53	91.68 ± 4.71	-2.80 ± 0.56	-3.91 to -1.69	<0.001
Control	93.13 ± 4.72	93.65 ± 4.92			

Notes: *Adjusted for confounding variables (sex, education level, age, duration since diagnosis, number of medications, presence of comorbidities, distance to healthcare facility, and travel time to healthcare facility); SD: Standard Deviation; MA: Medication Adherence; SBP: Systolic Blood Pressure; DBP: Diastolic Blood Pressure; CI: Confidence Interval; Statistical significance at $p < 0.05$.

The DiD analysis indicated that the intervention significantly improved all outcomes, adjusting for sex, education, age, time since diagnosis, number of medications, comorbidities, distance, and travel time to healthcare facilities. The intervention group showed a 1.72-point greater increase in knowledge ($p = 0.001$), a 6.16-point higher increase in self-efficacy ($p < 0.001$), and a 1.28-point higher increase in medication adherence compared with the control group. Clinically, the intervention group experienced a meaningful reduction in systolic blood pressure by 9.67 mmHg ($p < 0.001$) and diastolic blood pressure by 2.80 mmHg ($p < 0.001$) compared with the control group. These findings provide strong evidence that the hybrid HBM-based intervention causally improves behavioural and clinical outcomes (Table 3).

Discussion

This study demonstrates that the HHEI-HBM significantly improves knowledge, self-efficacy, and medication adherence, and reduces systolic and diastolic blood pressure among rural hypertensive patients. These findings align with previous research, confirming that HBM-based health education, delivered face-to-face or through digital platforms, is effective in improving psychological outcomes and reducing blood pressure among hypertensive patients. The study by Kurnia et al. (2020) in Indonesia demonstrated that a health education programme significantly improved patients' knowledge ($p = 0.000$) and attitudes ($p = 0.008$) in hypertension management. Similarly, Bakhshi et al. (2023) reported that three months after receiving HBM-based education, the medication adherence score in the intervention group (6.63 ± 1.71) increased significantly compared to the control group (5.29 ± 1.85 ; $p = 0.006$). In addition, the main components of HBM, including perceived benefits, perceived self-efficacy, and perceived barriers, also showed significant improvement in the intervention group ($p < 0.001$).

From a clinical perspective, Shen et al. (2020) found that HBM-based educational interventions delivered via WhatsApp reduced systolic blood pressure by 7.37 mmHg ($p = 0.001$) and diastolic blood pressure by 4.07 mmHg ($p = 0.014$). The study also reported that perceived susceptibility and self-efficacy significantly influenced blood pressure lowering. In line with these findings, Xu et al. (2026) reported that six weeks after video-based health education, improvements in exercise adherence, blood pressure control, knowledge, attitudes, and self-efficacy were observed among women with gestational hypertension.

Jiang (2020) reported that face-to-face communication influences subsequent online interactions, as initial direct contact strengthens therapeutic relationships, with trust and satisfaction moderating this link. Single-modality interventions have limitations: digital-only approaches may lack personal contact, while face-to-face alone may lack continuity. Therefore, integrating both modalities, as implemented in the HHEI-HBM model, combines direct interaction with continuous digital engagement to improve adherence and sustain behaviour change, supporting evidence that hybrid models are suitable for rural and resource-limited settings.

The HHEI-HBM intervention was based on key HBM constructs. Educational materials elicited perceived threats and benefits, including risks of complications such as stroke, benefits of antihypertensive medication, and management of side effects. The WhatsApp group enabled patients to revisit materials, receive reminders, and engage in peer exchange, serving as cues to action and enhancing self-efficacy. Combined online and face-to-face interactions facilitated discussion and problem-solving, reducing perceived barriers and supporting adherence. For example, concerns about the harmful effects of long-term antihypertensive use on kidney function were addressed by healthcare staff and reinforced through videos showing how treatment prevents organ damage. These interactions likely corrected misconceptions, strengthened perceived severity and benefits, and supported adherence.

Overall, the study reinforces that HBM-based hybrid interventions, combining direct and digital methods, consistently improve psychological outcomes and clinical measures in hypertensive patients, highlighting the importance of context-adaptive, theory-driven approaches for effective hypertension control.

The intervention's health education content was developed using the HBM, which positions knowledge as the basis for shaping perceptions of threats and benefits. By increasing knowledge, individuals are better equipped to make informed health decisions and adopt behaviour changes. The HBM emphasises perceptions, beliefs, and cues to action as key determinants of behaviour (Alyafei & Easton-Carr, 2025). This model explains that individuals are more likely to take health-related action when they perceive a threat, consider their health goals important, and believe that the recommended action is effective. This theoretical foundation supports the use of the HBM in developing adaptive, contextually tailored hybrid health education interventions.

The consistency between the theoretical foundation and empirical findings is evident in various previous studies. A study in Indonesia involving 180 patients with hypertension found that HBM constructs were associated with adherence to hypertension treatment (Suhart et al., 2022). Similarly, Al-Noumani et al. (2018) in Oman reported that higher self-efficacy (OR 2.59; 95% CI 1.54 to 4.37), stronger beliefs in the necessity of medication (OR 1.98; 95% CI 1.21 to 3.23), and lower concerns about medication (OR 0.34; 95% CI 0.20 to 0.57) were associated with better medication adherence. In addition, high adherence was also associated with a lower likelihood of uncontrolled blood pressure (OR 0.47; 95% CI 0.24 to 0.93). These findings further reinforce that strengthening HBM constructs in the development of educational content is an evidence-based and

relevant approach to improving adherence and clinical outcomes among patients with hypertension in rural areas.

Health education using diverse approaches and media for patients with hypertension in rural areas is both appropriate and relevant, especially considering the persistent gap between rural and urban populations. A meta-analysis of 299 surveys across 66 low- and middle-income countries, involving approximately 19.8 million participants, showed that although the prevalence of hypertension was slightly higher in urban areas (30.5%) than in rural areas (27.9%), the increase occurred more rapidly in rural settings, significantly narrowing the urban and rural gap from 5.75% (1990 to 2004) to 1.38% (2005 to 2020) (Ranzani et al., 2022).

Health education for patients with hypertension in rural areas is also consistent with findings from a study in China, which showed that rural patients with hypertension had lower levels of health education and medication adherence compared to their urban counterparts, along with differences in hypertension management practices (Tam et al., 2023). A study in Indonesia similarly reported lower adherence in rural areas (23.6%) than in urban areas (38.2%; $p=0.000$), with adherence strongly associated with knowledge of hypertension and educational level (Rikmasari et al., 2023). Overall, this evidence indicates that rural areas are significant contributors to the burden of hypertension in LMICs. Therefore, hypertension control, including strengthening health education programmes, should explicitly prioritise targeted, context-specific interventions in rural settings. Limited internet connectivity remains a key challenge in rural Indonesia. In addition, disparities in access to devices, digital literacy, and passive participation further constrain sustained engagement with digital health interventions (Wahab, 2025). These limitations highlight the constraints of digital-only approaches and underscore the importance of hybrid models that integrate face-to-face interaction to maintain engagement and support hypertension management. Furthermore, community-based strategies, such as involving local health workers, can reinforce patient engagement in low-resource settings.

Social support plays a crucial role in shaping health behaviours in rural Indonesian communities with strong collectivist values, and is a key determinant of medication adherence (Rikmasari et al., 2023). In this context, family support, as a primary form of social support, reinforces perceived benefits, provides cues to action such as medication reminders, and enhances self-efficacy through emotional and practical assistance. It may improve adherence and complements the hybrid educational approach, particularly in settings with limited healthcare access.

This study has several limitations. Participant selection was not randomised, which may limit generalisability, and the six-week follow-up did not allow assessment of long-term sustainability. Additionally, the difference-in-differences analysis used only two time points, so the parallel trends assumption could not be formally tested. However, baseline equivalence between groups was confirmed, and relevant covariates were included to minimise potential confounding, maintaining adequate internal validity. Future studies should include longer follow-up periods to assess the intervention's sustainability and possible long-term clinical impact. In addition, randomised study designs are recommended to strengthen causal inference.

Conclusion

The study results indicate that the HBM-based Hybrid Health Educational Intervention is effective in improving knowledge about hypertension, enhancing self-efficacy, increasing medication adherence, and reducing both systolic and diastolic blood pressure among hypertensive patients in rural areas. Therefore, it can be integrated into health promotion programmes at CHCs. In addition, district health offices may consider its inclusion in standard training for community health workers to strengthen community-based hypertension management. Furthermore, these findings provide evidence of an alternative health education model to improve medication adherence among hypertensive patients in LMICs facing resource limitations, particularly shortages of healthcare personnel.

Declarations

AI Use Statement: AI-assisted technology (Grammarly) was used solely for grammar refinement and language editing during manuscript preparation. The authors take full responsibility for the content, interpretation, and conclusions presented in this manuscript.

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Ethical Approval: This study received ethical approval from the Ethics Committee of the Faculty of Medicine, Sebelas Maret University (Number 191/UN27.06.11/KEP/EC/2024) and was registered with the Indonesia Clinical Research Registry (INA-KR5CN0X). All participants received written and verbal information and provided written informed consent prior to participation.

Author Contributions: Mustara, Hartono, and Eti Poncorini Pamungkasari designed the research methodology and conceptual framework. Mustara conducted the investigation, data collection, data curation, formal analysis, and manuscript drafting. Hartono and Eti Poncorini Pamungkasari supervised the study, validated the findings, and contributed to manuscript review and editing. All authors have read and approved the final version of the manuscript.

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